

Abstract

Electroacupuncture and Acupuncture in the Treatment of Anxiety: A Double-Blinded Randomised Parallel Clinical Trial.

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Abstract

Anxiety disorders currently represent one of the leading causes of disability globally, affecting approximately 301 million people worldwide (WHO, 2023), with a significant impact on cognitive, physiological, and socio-professional functioning. Given the high prevalence and existing therapeutic limitations—including cases of partial response or non-response to anxiolytic medication—it is pertinent to investigate complementary approaches based on scientific evidence.

This presentation provided an integrated analysis of the efficacy of manual acupuncture and electroacupuncture in treating anxiety, framing their foundations in the light of both Traditional Chinese Medicine and contemporary neurophysiology. The underlying neurobiological mechanisms were discussed, including the activation of A δ and C afferent fibres, modulation of the hypothalamus–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis, the release of neuromodulators (such as β -endorphins and enkephalins), and the influence on prefrontal cortex and limbic system activity.

The presentation integrated three main components:

- Systematic Literature Review (2007–2017): Highlighting consistency in the reduction of anxiety levels through acupuncture, despite a scarcity of robust clinical studies regarding electroacupuncture.
- Retrospective Study in an Integrative Medicine Context: Demonstrating a significant reduction in anxiety after five treatment sessions, regardless of whether patients were taking psychotropic medication.
- Randomised, Double-Blinded, Parallel Clinical Trial: Comparing acupuncture and electroacupuncture using a standardised 10-session protocol. The BAI, GAD-7, and OASIS scales were used, alongside salivary cortisol monitoring.

The results demonstrated:

- A significant reduction in anxiety levels after 5 and 10 sessions.
- A parallel decrease in morning salivary cortisol.

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- Similar efficacy between manual acupuncture and electroacupuncture.
- Results independent of the concomitant use of anxiolytic medication.

In conclusion, a standardised protocol of acupuncture and/or electroacupuncture is effective in reducing anxiety levels, with a clinically relevant onset of effect after the fifth session and maintenance until the tenth session. These data support the integration of this approach as a therapeutic adjunct in the treatment of anxiety within conventional clinical settings, contributing to a more integrative, evidence-based, and patient-centred medicine.

Keywords: Traditional Chinese Medicine; Integrative Medicine; Acupuncture; Electroacupuncture; Personalised Medicine; Anxiety.

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